

Understanding the behavioral factors influencing farmers' future adoption of climate-smart agriculture: A multi-group analysis

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Climate-smart agriculture
Adoption intention
Multi-group analysis
Behavioural factors

ABSTRACT

The transition to climate-smart agriculture (CSA) is essential for sustainable food production, yet adoption varies widely due to differences in farmers' experiences, motivations, and constraints. Following an extended Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) framework, this study examines the factors shaping future CSA adoption intentions among adopters and non-adopters. The findings reveal distinct adoption pathways. Positive attitudes toward CSA significantly influence adoption across all groups. Perceived behavioral control (PBC) enhances adoption intentions among non-adopters and CSA practice adopters, while social norms strongly motivate non-adopters to initiate adoption. Perceived compatibility with existing systems, values, and experiences drives the adoption of CSA practices, whereas perceived ease of use is more influential for CSA technology adoption. Additionally, economic motives primarily drive the continued adoption of CSA technologies, whereas non-economic motives encourage the continued implementation of CSA practices. Risk aversion significantly hinders CSA technology adoption. These insights underscore the importance of tailored strategies reflecting group-specific behavioral drivers. To enhance CSA adoption, peer-to-peer learning and advisory support are recommended for non-adopters, compatibility-driven awareness for practice adopters, and economic and technical support mechanisms for technology adopters.

1. Introduction

The world's population is projected to reach 9.7 billion in 2050 (United Nations, 2022), requiring a transformation of agriculture to feed a growing population while simultaneously reducing its negative climate impact (Thornton et al., 2017). Agriculture is both vulnerable to climate change and a contributor to climate change, primarily through its greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Azadi et al., 2022). To address the dual challenge while ensuring food security, the concept of Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) was introduced by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (Lipper and Zilberman, 2018). CSA aims to sustainably increase agricultural productivity, build resilience to climate change, and reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Lipper et al., 2018). The concept of CSA was first presented at the Hague Conference on Agriculture, Food Security, and Climate Change in 2010 (Thottadi and Singh, 2024). In 2013, a joint effort of several international organizations, a CSA sourcebook was developed, offering an important

guiding framework for its implementation (FAO, 2013). Furthermore, the Global Alliance for Climate-Smart Agriculture (GACSA) was established in 2014 with the aim of bridging science and policy through a focus on three key action areas: knowledge, enabling environments, and investments (Lipper and Zilberman, 2018).

CSA implementation is highly context-specific and often involves trade-offs between its three pillars (Thornton et al., 2017). Maximizing synergies between these goals through locally adapted solutions is central to CSA's effectiveness (Mwongera et al., 2017). Globally, CSA gained further interest through the CSA Action Plan presented at the 2014 UN Climate Summit and has since been widely acknowledged in national adaptation plans (Azadi et al., 2022). For instance, of the 113 countries that included adaptation measures in their Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDCs) to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) by the end of 2015, nearly all prioritized agriculture, with about 30 % explicitly referencing CSA (Richards et al., 2015; Thornton et al., 2017). While most countries

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.145632>

Received 29 December 2024; Received in revised form 13 April 2025; Accepted 1 May 2025

Available online 2 May 2025

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have developed CSA strategies, the development and implementation of formal CSA policy frameworks have progressed slowly due to changes in the coordination approach (Fathi et al., 2023). For instance, in Africa's CSA Implementation Plan from 2022 to 2032, only about half adopted the CSA policy frameworks in place (Davila et al., 2024).

CSA does not necessarily require entirely new farming practices but rather builds on existing practices, guiding them toward greater sustainability (Lipper et al., 2014). However, prioritizing CSA within the policy framework remains complex due to its multi-dimensional nature (Thornton et al., 2017). Several barriers impede the CSA implementation, like limited enabling policies and financing (Partey et al., 2018), risk aversion and perceived benefit uncertainty (Pedersen et al., 2024), weak integration of information resources (Zhao et al., 2023), and high labor demands (Agyekum et al., 2024). Governments and international organizations such as FAO and the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research, non-governmental organizations and civil society organizations have initiated different initiatives to overcome the barriers and to scale up and out the CSA (Ma and Rahut, 2024). However, CSA adoption rates remain low at the global level (Li et al., 2024).

The European Union (EU) has not directly included CSA as policy framework (Casares Guillén and Pazos-Vidal, 2024), but it has embedded CSA principles within its broader EU sustainability and climate goals (Morkunas and Volkov, 2023). For instance, the Farm-to-Fork Strategy, one of the EU's Green Deal initiatives, seeks to make food systems more sustainable and environmentally friendly (EC, 2024). In this context, the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) supports environmentally sustainable farming (EC, 2023), particularly through eco-schemes designed to encourage the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (Boix-Fayos and De Vente, 2023). Despite these efforts, the adoption rate of such practices remains slow (Gemtou et al., 2024). Given that contextualizing CSA within existing policy frameworks is a key component of its approach (Thornton et al., 2017), a recent review by Erekaló et al. (2024) assessed and identified different CSA in Europe. Several barriers continue to hinder CSA implementation, including economic (e.g. high short-term cost) (Thottadi and Singh, 2024), technology-related (e.g. lack of skills) (Pedersen et al., 2024) and regulatory challenges (e.g. legislation regarding some scheme) (Verschuuren, 2018). This highlights the need for targeted interventions (Long et al., 2016) and considerable capacity development (Pedersen et al., 2024) to facilitate broader adoption.

Behavioural factors are increasingly recognized for shaping farmers' adoption decisions in sustainable agriculture (Dessart et al., 2019). Previous empirical studies have identified various behavioural factors influencing the adoption of different CSA, such as precision agricultural technologies (Kakkavou et al., 2024), sustainable agricultural practices (Menozi et al., 2015), and sustainable innovations more broadly (Rizzo et al., 2023). A deeper understanding of farmer motivations is therefore crucial for explaining how these behaviours drive adoption decisions (Brown et al., 2021). Recently, research has increasingly emphasized on the role of which behavioural factors in shaping farmers' decisions to adopt or reject CSA (Gemtou et al., 2024). Different studies have linked different behavioural factors to adoption of CSA, for instance, bio-based fertilizer (Garmendia-Lemus et al., 2024), spot spraying (Feisthauer et al., 2024), microbial application (Tensi et al., 2022), reduced tillage (Bijtebier et al., 2018), mixed cropping (Bonke and Musshoff, 2020) and nutrient management (Daxini et al., 2019). These findings highlight the need for further research on understanding the socio-psychological lever for implementing sustainable agriculture and also the structural barriers hindering the uptake (Swart et al., 2023).

The influence of behavioural factors on adoption decisions often differs between adopters and non-adopters due to variations in experiences (Kerneckner et al., 2020), knowledge (Barnes et al., 2019), and perceived barriers (Myers and Wilson, 2023). This variation has been supported by earlier studies on the adoption of smart farming technologies (Giua et al., 2022) and CSA practices more generally CSA practices (Kirungi et al., 2023). Although previous research has acknowledged

these variations, limited attention has been given to the heterogeneity in adoption decision-making stemming from farmers' CSA implementation experiences. To address this gap, exploring the factors determining the adoption decision-making based on farmers' previous experiences—adopters or non-adopters—can provide nuanced evidence to understand future adoption decisions better (Kerneckner et al., 2020). This study seeks to answer the key question: What motivates farmers to implement CSA—both among those who have already adopted CSA and those who have not (yet) adopted CSA—and how do motivations differ between CSA practices and CSA technologies?

Assuming the population is homogeneous may lead to misleading conclusions. One way to address heterogeneity is to partition the data based on observable characteristics and estimate the model separately for each partition, thus accounting for observed heterogeneity (Vaithilingam et al., 2024). On the other hand, multi-group analysis (MGA) in structural equation modeling is a recommended approach for addressing such heterogeneity based on predefined subgroups (Troiville et al., 2025). This study applies MGA to gain a better understanding of CSA adoption dynamics.

Specifically, this study explores how CSA implementation experiences shape the key factors influencing future adoption decisions, as past behaviour can influence the impact of other behavioural factors (Vallejos B et al., 2023). Depending on their level of adoption, behavioural factors may differently shape farmers' intentions to adopt CSA (Borges and Lansink, 2015). In this context, two types of future adoption decision-making are considered for predicting adoption intention: those who plan to start implementing CSA (non-adopters) and those who intend to continue (adopters). The hypothesis for this study builds on the premise that differences between adopters and non-adopters shape future adoption decisions, driven by variations in attitudes, perceptions toward CSA, social influences, and farming goals (Läpple and Rensburg, 2011). Therefore, by examining the motivational factors driving future CSA adoption decisions among farmers, those with prior CSA implementation experience, and those who have not yet implemented CSA, this research contributes valuable insights for promoting CSA adoption by providing more targeted evidence.

2. Background

In this section, we present the theoretical approach and contextual information. As a natural extension, we put forward the hypotheses of this study.

2.1. Theoretical framework

Various theoretical frameworks have been used to capture the behavioural aspects influencing the adoption of CSA. For example, Long et al. (2016) followed a framework by categorizing the factors into supply-side and demand-side determinants through an exploratory approach. Dessart et al. (2019) employed an integrated framework for analyzing behavioural factors that influence the adoption of sustainable practices. They distinguish between factors as either distal (meaning not directly related to CSA) or proximal (meaning directly associated with CSA). Dessart et al. (2019) further refined the framework by categorizing the behavioural factors along the distal–proximal spectrum into three groups: dispositional factors (mainly distal, related to stable internal attributes such as individual farming goals, preferences, and risk aversions), social factors (proximal or distal, stemming from interactions with others, such as social norms), and cognitive factors (mainly proximal, involving learning and reasoning, such as perceived benefits and costs, perceived behavioural control and attitude towards the behaviour). These categories align with the supply-demand framework suggested by Long et al. (2016) but place greater emphasis on behavioural aspects, which is the primary focus of this study. Although several theories and models have been developed to predict decision-making in sustainable agricultural practices, a recent literature review by

Thompson et al. (2023) highlights the limited employment of behavioural theoretical frameworks. It also suggests incorporating such behavioural frameworks as an essential tool for a more comprehensive analysis of predictors influencing the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices.

Among behavioural theoretical frameworks, the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991) is one of the most widely used models for predicting pro-environmental (Sok et al., 2021). It is a well-established socio-psychological framework (Syed et al., 2024) designed to predict individual decision-making through three core constructs: attitudes (perceived benefits of implementing the behavior), subjective norms (perceived social pressures), and PBC (perceived self-efficacy and controllability) (Despotović et al., 2019). TPB is widely regarded as a foundational framework for many other behavioural models (Jiang et al., 2018) due to its versatility and strong predictive power in explaining behavioural intentions (Wei et al., 2025). The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is another behavioural model that considers perceived usefulness, ease of use, and intended use of technology as predictors of technology acceptance (Turner et al., 2010). However, TAM has been criticized for oversimplifying the technology acceptance process, as adoption decisions often involve more complex factors beyond the technology itself (Thomas et al., 2023). Similarly, the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory is another framework that focuses on the diffusion process and perceived attributes of technology, such as relative advantage, complexity, compatibility, trialability, observability, communication channels and social systems, to predict adoption (Call and Herber, 2022). Another behavioural model that focuses on values as motivation to predict adoption decisions is the value-belief-norm (VBN) theory (Zhang et al., 2020). This study adopts the TPB framework because it serves as a foundational model for predicting behavioral intentions while allowing for the integration of additional contextual factors from other frameworks. TPB was chosen because it effectively balances internal beliefs (attitudes, perceived control) (De Groot and Steg, 2007) and external influences (social norms) (Syed et al., 2024) in predicting behavioral intentions.

While the original TPB, which focuses on three core factors, provides a robust foundation, extending it to include both internal and external contextual factors may improve its ability to explain adoption decisions better (De Lauwere et al., 2022). Given its flexibility in terms of application across various fields (Yuriev et al., 2020), openness to extensions—allowing for the incorporation of additional cognitive, motivational, and contextual factors relevant to a specific domain (De Lauwere et al., 2022) and its ability to integrate with complementary behavioural models (Acikgoz et al., 2023), extended TPB was adopted for this study to enhance its explanatory power for complex behavioural changes, including the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (Savari and Gharechae, 2020). Several previous studies have extended the original TPB framework to predict various agricultural and environmental behaviors, such as farmers' adaptation and mitigation strategies for climate change (Zhang et al., 2020), farmers' adoption of agroforestry practices (Leduc and Hansson, 2024), farmers' decision-making in the transition towards circular agriculture (De Lauwere et al., 2022), intention to use spot spraying (Feisthauer et al., 2024), decisions to continue with agri-environmental schemes, intentions to adopt nutrient management planning (Daxini et al., 2018), intention for safe use of chemical fertilizers (Savari and Gharechae, 2020) and green manure technology (Valizadeh et al., 2023).

This study extends the core TPB factors by incorporating contextual and other relevant factors to explain CSA adoption intentions better, as these factors provide deeper insights into the motivators of behavioural change (Valizadeh et al., 2023). The first two contextual factors—perceived compatibility and perceived complexity—were included as TPB extensions to capture farmers' perceptions of CSA, as implementing CSA practices and technologies requires new knowledge and skills (Isakhanyan et al., 2024) and must fit into existing farming systems (Pedersen et al., 2024). These two proximal cognitive factors, as they

directly relate to farmers' perceptions of the attributes of CSA practices and technologies (Acikgoz et al., 2023), are considered TPB extensions. While perceived compatibility and perceived complexity may seem conceptually similar to PBC—which primarily captures self-efficacy and controllability (Ajzen, 2011)—they are distinct constructs. PBC does not explicitly account for how farmers perceive the technology attributes themselves. To address this, we incorporate farmers' perceptions about two CSA attributes, namely perceived ease of use (from TAM) and perceived complexity (from DOI), to better capture farmers' perceived evaluations of CSA attributes. Additionally, attitude toward the behavior, which reflects farmers' beliefs about the benefits of CSA adoption (Li et al., 2020), is also distinct from perceived compatibility and perceived ease of use. Unlike PBC and attitudes, perceived compatibility and perceived ease of use measure how farmers assess CSA's attributes—whether it aligns with their farming operations and whether it is perceived as difficult to implement (Shang et al., 2021). Therefore, it is essential to assess the role of perceived complexity and ease of CSA on future adoption decisions (Kaine and Wright, 2022).

Another TPB extension in this study includes a broader spectrum of motivational factors, such as farming motives (Trujillo-Barrera et al., 2016), risk aversion (Rodríguez-Barillas et al., 2024) and the extent of the use of learning environments and networks of expertise for sustainable agricultural advisory services (Bavorová et al., 2020). Incorporating these constructs tailored to CSA practices and technologies to extend original TBP constructs is essential to better understanding future CSA adoption decision-making. The included constructs, for instance, farmers' perceptions about CSA—specifically, perceived compatibility and ease of use, which are proximal cognitive factors—play a significant role in shaping their adoption decisions (Dong et al., 2022). This aligns with the DOI theory, which asserts that the acceptance of practices or technologies is shaped by individuals' perceptions of their characteristics (Dearing, 2009).

In addition, dispositional factors, such as farming motives, are essential to further capture the drivers of farmers' engagement in sustainable food production based on their farming objectives (Schattman et al., 2021). Including individual farming business motives can lead to variation in adoption decision prediction on top of perceptions about sustainable practice (Hoek et al., 2021). Thus, farming motives were considered and measured in terms of farming business motives—both economic (e.g., reducing input costs) and non-economic (e.g., environmental or sociocultural goals), as highlighted by Trujillo-Barrera et al. (2016). Notably, non-economic motive dimensions may also go beyond the general environmental and social concerns to include values-based goals, such as stewardship or self-identity (Dessart et al., 2019). In addition, risk aversion, a personality trait, was considered to capture farmers' general risk aversion attitudes associated with financial investment, which may hinder future adoption decision-making (Nainggolan et al., 2023).

Furthermore, the use of different agricultural training service networks was considered, given their influence in shaping farmers' adoption decision-making by improving the level of knowledge and experience (Bavorová et al., 2020). Farmers with prior experience in CSA may have different expectations and decision-making patterns than those without such experience, which can influence their future adoption plans (Kerneck et al., 2020). Thus, the influence of behavioural factors may vary between adopters and non-adopters of sustainable agriculture (Barnes et al., 2019). In line with research on how past behavior informs future intentions (Vallejos B et al., 2023), this study employed the MGA by classifying farmers based on their CSA implementation experience. Additionally, to account for heterogeneity, both observed factors such as age, farm size, education level, cooperative membership, and unobserved contextual differences stemming from regional differences, country-level variations were incorporated as determinants of adoption decisions (Kerneck et al., 2020). Based on the original TPB framework and the inclusion of contextual extension factors, the theoretical framework for this study is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Extended TPB framework to explain the future adoption decisions of CSA.

2.2. Hypotheses development

2.2.1. Hypotheses on the original TPB behavioral factors

This study formulates the following hypotheses to investigate the relationships between the factors and adoption intention. Attitude relates to the extent to which an individual holds a positive or negative assessment of the behavior (Ajzen, 1991). This can capture an individual's general evaluation of engaging in the behavior—whether they perceive it as beneficial or detrimental based on expected outcomes (Valizadeh et al., 2023). Farmers' attitudes, a proximal cognitive factor, are expressed in this study as an evaluation of the perceived benefits of adopting sustainable agriculture (Li et al., 2023), which could influence intentions to adopt (Block et al., 2024). For implementing sustainable farming practices and technologies, farmers could weigh the perceived benefits of CSA in terms of higher output, lower costs, less workload, and higher returns (Block et al., 2024). These perceived benefits, in turn, influence farmers' adoption decisions (Bopp et al., 2019). Thus, the first hypothesis is as follows: **H1:** A positive attitude toward CSA practices and technology is expected to influence future adoption decisions positively.

Social norms represent peer learning and reference group confirmation that could influence an individual's intention to implement a given behavior (Hüttel et al., 2022). The desire to fit in, maintain social status, and avoid disapproval can lead farmers to adopt sustainable practices that are perceived as the norm or are socially acceptable within their community (Le Coent et al., 2021). This was also confirmed by Hüttel et al. (2022), who highlighted the role of social norms in shaping the adoption of sustainable agriculture. Hence, we hypothesize the following: **H2:** Social norms are expected to affect farmers' future adoption decisions positively.

PBC, one of the proximal cognitive factors, represents individual

farmers' beliefs about their confidence in their ability (Luh et al., 2023), resources, knowledge, and capability to adopt and how much they control over adopting CSA practices (Rezaei et al., 2019). It represents the farmers' confidence in their ability and control over resources that influence their willingness to implement sustainable agriculture (Bonke and Musshoff, 2020). Daxini et al. (2019) found that individual farmers' perceptions of their abilities and control of resources significantly influence the intention to adopt sustainable agricultural practices. Thus, **H3:** PBC is expected to influence future CSA adoption decisions positively.

2.2.2. Hypotheses on the TPB extension factors

Perceptions of the compatibility and complexity of CSA significantly impact farmers' intentions to adopt (Kirungi et al., 2023). These proximal TPB extensions that capture the farmers' perceptions of attributes (compatibility and complexity) of practice or technology (Acikgoz et al., 2023) are separated in this study from the core TPB factors PBC, which are more captured by self-efficacy as well as controllability individual (Ajzen, 2011) and attitude towards sustainable agricultural practice that captures beliefs on benefits of adoption (Bopp et al., 2019). Perceptions of the compatibility and complexity of CSA significantly impact farmers' intentions to adopt (Kirungi et al., 2023). In this study, perceived compatibility reflects the degree to which individual perceptions of how well CSA integrates with farmers' current farming systems and experiences (Shang et al., 2021). Perceptions of the compatibility of technology positively influence their intention to use technology (Li et al., 2023). Thus, **H4:** Perceived compatibility is expected to be positively associated with CSA adoption intentions.

Perceived ease of use, on the other hand, represents farmers' perceptions of how ease of use or difficulty of CSA implementation could influence the adoption intentions of CSA (Kirungi et al., 2023). It was

indicated that perceived ease of use of technology is significantly and positively associated with technology adoption intention (Saengavut and Jirasathumb, 2021). Thus, **H5**: Perceived ease of use of CSA is expected to correlate with future adoption decisions positively.

Even though adopting CSA may entail both costs and benefits for farmers (Long et al., 2016), farmers' general farming motives encompass not only economic but also non-economic aspects that individual farmers' lifestyles could influence (Dessart et al., 2019). For instance, Kallas et al. (2010) indicated that the decision to adopt organic farming was predicted positively by the farmers' environmental objective over the economic. Individual farm business motives—whether economic, environmental, or sociocultural—can significantly influence farmers' pro-environmental behaviour (Hoek et al., 2021). In this study, the farm business motives represent farmers' overall goals regarding their business activity, encompassing both economic and noneconomic aspects. Trujillo-Barrera et al. (2016) found a positive influence of economic motives on the adoption of sustainable practices. As a result, **H6**: Farm businesses' economic motives are expected to influence the adoption of CSA positively in the future.

On the other hand, noneconomic motives reflect that farmers are linked with environmental, social, and moral concerns (low emissions, public health care, animal welfare, and fair prices) (Howley, 2015; Pagliacci et al., 2020). The non-economic motives of farmers have a significant and positive association with the adoption of sustainable technology (Trujillo-Barrera et al., 2016). Thus, **H7**: The non-economic motive of the farm business is hypothesized to have a positive association with the intention to adopt CSA.

While making adoption decisions, other dispositional behavioural factors, namely farmer's general risk aversion—including preferring certainty over uncertainty, taking financial risks, and avoiding investment risk—could influence it (Ghali et al., 2022). Risk aversion negatively determines the farmer's future adoption decision-making (Rodríguez-Barillas et al., 2024). Accordingly, **H8**: Risk aversion is hypothesized to be negatively associated with the intention to adopt CSA.

The use of various agricultural training and advisory service sources—such as farmer training programs, farm visits, field demonstrations, field days, workshops, and advisory services—plays a crucial role in enhancing farmers' engagement in CSA by improving their knowledge and providing experiential learning opportunities (Caffaro et al., 2020). Hence, **H9**: The extent to which agricultural extension and advisory network training services are used is expected to influence the adoption of CSA positively.

Although this study focuses on behavioural factors, previous research has highlighted the inclusion of observed socioeconomic factors as a control variable to capture observed heterogeneity issues (Rezaei et al., 2019). Among the socioeconomic factors, farmer age, education level, farm size, and cooperative membership are dominant determinants of adoption decisions (Rizzo et al., 2023). Accordingly, this study includes age, farm size, education level, and cooperative membership as control variables in the analysis of CSA adoption decisions. Furthermore, while analyzing the influence of behavioural factors across multiple countries, it is essential to account for regional differences, as pro-environmental behaviour dynamics may vary by location (Saari et al., 2021). Therefore, this study includes a country dummy variable as a control factor to capture potential regional variations in CSA adoption decisions.

3. Research methodology

3.1. Research design

This study followed a structured research approach to investigate the behavioural factors influencing farmers' future adoption decisions of CSA. Considering the nature of our objectives, it began with a comprehensive literature review to identify relevant decision-making factors for CSA adoption and potential theoretical framework foundations. In

parallel, relevant measurement items (indicators) were identified from the literature for the TPB and its extension constructs. These identified items were reviewed and refined through consultations with BEATLES project¹ partners, ensuring conceptual clarity and contextual relevance to the European agricultural setting. Following this preparatory phase, the study employed an online survey to collect empirical data across multiple EU countries. It consisted of survey design and data collection, construct measurement, reliability and validity assessment, hypothesis testing and MGA. To enhance clarity, Fig. 2 provides an overview of the methodological design, highlighting key steps, including input data, analysis techniques, and expected outcomes.

3.2. The survey of instruments development

Considering the nature of our study objectives, this research followed a structured approach to investigating the behavioural factors influencing farmers' future adoption decisions of CSA. The survey instrument development began with a comprehensive literature review to identify relevant decision-making frameworks and theoretical foundations. Given the study's focus on behavioural decision-making factors for the adoption of CSA, different constructs were included. All constructs presented (Fig. 1) are based on multiple items following the theoretical considerations and empirical validation from prior studies. Based on existing validated scales from previous studies, relevant measurement items were identified to operationalize the behavioural constructs to measure cognitive, dispositional, and social factors influencing CSA adoption. A seven-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree), was used to measure the latent behavioural constructs explored in the study. The drafted initial questionnaire was shared with BEATLES partners for consultations and review to ensure its contextual relevance to the European agriculture setting and conceptual clarity. Based on the feedback, the questionnaire was refined. The questionnaire consists of two parts: the first focuses on the final refined behavioural constructs items with each three-to six-dimensional statement, and the second focuses on the respondents' socio-demographic and economic characteristics. The dependent variable in this study, intention to adopt, captures farmers' future CSA adoption decisions. To minimize response bias from participants' unfamiliarity with the CSA concept, the survey began with a concise textual description of CSA, complemented by visual and textual examples of climate-smart farming practices and technologies. This description highlighted CSA implementation outcomes and included practical examples of CSAs. Subsequently, the respondents were asked about their familiarity with CSA, followed by a question regarding the specific CSAs they were implementing. The modified questionnaire was pilot tested with 24 respondents for final modification and to confirm internal consistency. The final updated questions based on pilot test feedback were distributed to the respondents.

The measurement of adoption intention is operationalized based on the items of indicators validated, for instance, by Bagheri et al. (2019). PBC is measured using items adapted from Senger et al. (2017) and Syan et al. (2019), capturing farmers' perceived ability and resources to implement CSA practices. Attitudes toward CSA adoption were assessed using items grounded in the work of Nguyen and Drakou (2021), focusing on the perceived benefits of CSA, including productivity, cost-efficiency, and operational ease. Social norms were measured using items adapted from Hüttel et al. (2022), reflecting the influence of peers, community, and significant others on farmers' adoption decisions. The

¹ Behavioral Change Toward Climate-Smart Agriculture (BEATLES) is a EU horizon 2020 funded project that aspires to identify the behavioral, systemic and policy lock-ins and levers that influence entire food systems behavioral change and to develop transformation pathways of change to accelerate the systemic and systematic transition to climate-smart agriculture and smart farming technologies (<https://beatles-project.eu/>).

Fig. 2. Block box diagram illustrating the research methodology, the followed steps and their interconnection.

TPB extension contextual constructs focusing on proximal behavioural factors: Perceived ease of use was adopted from TAM. This construct was measured using items adapted from [Asare and Segarra \(2018\)](#), focusing on the simplicity and ease of implementing CSA practices ([Li et al., 2020](#)). Perceived compatibility: drawn from DOI, compatibility was assessed using items from [Syan et al. \(2019\)](#), emphasizing the alignment of CSA practices with farmers' goals, values, and workflows. Constructs focusing on dispositional behavioural factors for this study: farm business motives were measured using items more related to and [Trujillo-Barrera et al. \(2016\)](#), capturing both economic and non-economic motives. In addition, risk aversion was measured by items adopted from [Degieter et al. \(2023\)](#) to reflect farmers' preferences for certainty and their aversion to financial risks. Finally, perception of agricultural training and advisory services were measured using a Likert scale ranging from "never" to "always," for different sources of services use as employed by [Bavorová et al. \(2020\)](#), and on-farm demonstration service use ([Sutherland and Marchand, 2021](#)). This construct captures the frequency and extent to which farmers engage with training and advisory services. Based on previous literature, we included the dominant determinants of adoption decisions among the socioeconomic variables such as farmer age, education level, farm size, and cooperative membership ([Giua et al., 2022](#)).

3.3. Data collection and sampling strategy

An online survey was conducted to collect the intended data for this study as part of the EU Horizon 2020 BEATLES project. Data was collected from five European countries between December 20, 2022, and March 14, 2023. The questionnaire was initially developed in English, translated into local languages, and disseminated through various channels by the BEATLES project's local research partners, who served as use cases (UCs) in each country.

The BEATLES project has a local research partner as a UC in each country to facilitate data collection through their networks. UCs distributed the survey link via agricultural and institutional networks, farmer associations, and each UC's institutional link. Due to the difficulty of recruiting farmers through randomized response sampling, convenience sampling was employed. UCs utilized different institutional networks and channels for distribution, following a similar approach to [Scherfranz et al. \(2024\)](#). After excluding 31 incomplete responses, 691 observations were utilized for the analysis. Although we aimed for 100 responses per country within the survey timeframe, the final distribution

was uneven: Denmark (113), the Netherlands (82), Spain (131), Lithuania (298), and Slovenia (67). Computing the response rate was not feasible due to the voluntary response sampling method used, similar to [Tensi et al. \(2022\)](#). The sample may not be representative for the EU, as we followed convenience sampling techniques due to the reasons mentioned above and also the focus from the BEATLES project perspective with the aim of identification of individual, technological, and social decision-making factors from different EU countries, rather than country-wise analysis of these decision-making factors.

3.4. Data cleaning and preparations

After the exclusion of incomplete responses, based on the respondents' self-reported CSA implementation experience, we first categorized the respondents who described CSAs that they are currently implementing were classified as CSA adopters while the others were non-adopters. The CSA adopters were further grouped based on their self-reported lists of CSAs that they are currently implementing as CSA practice and CSA technology adopters. Thus, based on the number of farming practices or technologies they mentioned, we categorized CSA practice adopters as respondents who reported the implementation of farming practices like crop rotation, cover crops, crop diversification, intercropping, use of organic fertilizers, organic farming, use of inorganic fertilizer, or integrated pest management. CSA technology adopters were sampled respondents who had reported the implementation of smart farming technologies like precision fertilization, precision irrigation, variable rate application, or GPS-based guidance systems. If respondents had implemented more than one CSA alone or mixing practices and technologies, the farmer was assigned by the greater number described CSA, either practices or technologies. For multi-group analysis (MGA), this study was interested to examine whether the associations of the hypothesized behavior factors with future adoption decision vary across different farmers groups. Thus, the intention to adopt was categorized as the intention to start implementing CSA for those who are not currently implementing any CSA and the intention to continue implementing CSA for those who are currently implementing at least one CSA practice and or technology. This distinction allows for an in-depth exploration of the motivators and barriers influencing future adoption decisions in each group, offering nuanced insights into the decision-making process.

3.5. Data analysis framework

The Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) was employed to explore the association between the proposed constructs and CSA adoption intention due to the complex nature of the structural model, which includes multiple constructs (Hair et al., 2021). PLS-SEM was preferred over covariance-based SEM because of the complexity of the structural model, as it included multiple constructs (Hair et al., 2021). PLS-SEM was also preferred if the research aims to predict and identify key target constructs (Ringle et al., 2023). Furthermore, PLS-SEM provides considerable flexibility because it does not make restrictive assumptions about the distribution of the data and fitness to even small sample size (e.g., normality) (Hair et al., 2019) and has small sample size (Hair et al., 2022), which was the case for our multi-group analysis. The PLS-SEM approach has been applied to assess farmers' adoption behavior in agriculture, such as conservation agriculture (Savari et al., 2022), climate change adaptation (Zhang et al., 2020), mixed cropping (Bonke and Musshoff, 2020), sustainable agricultural practices (Bhujel and Joshi, 2023), on-farm silos (Vaz et al., 2020), smart farming technology (Feisthauer et al., 2024), green manure technologies (Valizadeh et al., 2023), and bio-based fertilizers (Garmendia-Lemus et al., 2024). Owing to the nature of heterogeneity in adoption behavior, in this study, a PLS-SEM approach with MGA was employed to assess whether the relationships differ across different groups of farmers (non-adopters, CSA-practice adopters, and CSA-technology adopters) (Ren and Zhong, 2022). The PLS-SEM approach consists of two parts: measurement and structural model. The nature of the constructs proposed for use in this study is unobservable (latent), requiring indirect measurement employing sets of observable indicators (items) that serve as proxies for the underlying construct (Hair et al., 2021).

3.5.1. Measurement model assessment

The first part is the empirical evaluation of the measurement model regarding the individual and composite reliabilities of their indicators (items) by assessing reliability statistics, such as factor loading, Cronbach's alpha, and average variance (Hair et al., 2021). The relationship between a latent construct and observable measurement indicators is important when measuring latent constructs (Rossiter, 2002). To evaluate the measurement model by assessing reliability and validity, factors loading, composite reliability, and convergent and discriminant validity were employed as quality criteria measurements (Hair et al., 2022). Reliability was evaluated through factor loading, Cronbach's Alpha (α) and Composite Reliability (CR) with $\rho_{ho,a}$ and $\rho_{ho,c}$ (Valizadeh et al., 2023), Convergent validity was assessed using Average Variance Extracted (AVE), while discriminant validity was evaluated using the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT), Fornell-Larcker criterion, and cross-loadings (Hair et al., 2022).

3.5.2. Structural model assessment

Following the measurement model satisfactory criteria evaluation, the second part of PLS-SEM, the structural model, analyzes the relationships between the independent latent constructs and the outcome to draw inferences on the hypothesized relationships (Hair et al., 2022). The model was assessed for collinearity issues, predictive power, model fit (SRMR), and out-of-sample predictive relevance (Q^2 Predict) (Feisthauer et al., 2024).

For the model estimation, we utilize the **SmartPLS4** (Ringle et al., 2024). Significance testing applied the bootstrapping procedure with 10,000 samples, the percentile approach, and a two-tailed test. We controlled the PLS-SEM results for observed control variables. Following the recommendations of (Hair et al., 2022) and inspired by Saari et al. (2021), we included countries, age, farm size, and education level as control variables in the PLS path model. Specifically, the country was included to account for regional differences and contextual differences by coding into four dummy-coded indicators, each representing a

different country, with the fifth Denmark in our study as a reference category. Similarly, we generated the age group as a category variable with five categories: 30–39 years (Age_2), 40–49 years (Age_3), 50–59 years (Age_4), and greater than 60 years (Age_5), with age less than 30 years (Age_1) as the reference category. For education level, we included two dummy-coded indicators representing vocational training (Education_2) and bachelor's degree and above (Education_3), with secondary school and below (Education_1) as the base category. Cooperative membership was included in the PLS path model as a dummy-coded control variable (0 = not a member and 1 = a member) single-item construct.

For pooled analysis, we included CSA adoption as a dummy variable in the PLS path model as a single construct. But, for MGA, we categorized the respondents into three groups: non-adopters, CSA adopters, and CSA technology adopters based on CSA implementation experience. As an estimation strategy, to assess whether the relationships differ across different adoption groups (non-adopters, CSA-practice adopters, and CSA-technology adopters) (Kirungi et al., 2023), we applied SmartPLS4 bootstrap MGA to identify significant differences in the effects of behavioural factors across the groups. Finally, we interpreted which behavioural factors were significantly different across groups and which factors were more influential for one group compared to another. This allowed us to assess how CSA adoption drivers influence vary between non-adopters, CSA practice adopters, and CSA technology adopters based on the SmartPLS4 bootstrapping MGA results (Cheah et al., 2023).

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive statistics

Fig. 3 shows the study participants' socioeconomic characteristics. The majority of respondents (48 %) have less than 50 ha, followed by 29 % who have more than 100 ha and 22 % who have between 51 and 100 ha. Regarding age distribution, the sample is relatively balanced across three age categories, with a slight bias toward respondents over 50 years. The age distribution seems consistent with Eurostat's 2020 data, which show that approximately 32 % of the agricultural labor force in the EU was under 40 years of age, while the remaining 58 % of farmers were aged 40 and above.² Regarding educational levels, the majority of respondents hold a bachelor's degree or higher, with a notable representation of those with vocational training. Finally, 43 % of sampled respondents are members of an agricultural cooperative or association, indicating significant participation in collective organizations. The descriptive statistics for all items used to measure behavioral constructs were presented in **Supplementary Material Table 1** for further reference.

4.2. Result and hypothesis testing

This subsection presents the measurement and structural model assessment, as well as the MGA results from the PLS-SEM model employed.

4.2.1. Measurement model

Following Hair et al. (2022), we evaluate the PLS-SEM measurement model by assessing reliability and validity. For reliability assessment, we evaluate factor loading for indicator reliability and Cronbach's Alpha (α) and Composite Reliability (CR) with $\rho_{ho,a}$ and $\rho_{ho,c}$ for internal consistency reliability. For validity assessment, we evaluate the convergent validity based on Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and discriminant validity based on Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT), Fornell-Larcker criterion, and cross-loading. We begin with an assessment of the factor

² https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Archi ve%3AFarmers_in_the_EU_-_statistics.

Fig. 3. Distribution of sample respondents by socio-economic characteristics (N = 691).

loading for the constructs. Four items: one from non-economic motive, two from economic motive and one from risk aversion were excluded due to their outer loading value being less than the critical value of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2022). Thus, the items with loading values greater than 0.7 were retained as they explain a substantial portion of the indicator's variance of the construct (Sarstedt et al., 2021) (see Table 1 below). The internal consistency reliability of the constructs was assessed based on CR (ρ_{a} and ρ_{c}) with results between 0.802 and 0.960, indicating good construct reliability (Hair et al., 2022). Furthermore, Cronbach's alpha (α), a measure of internal consistency reliability, shows good consistency indicators with the lowest value of 0.749, exceeding the threshold value of 0.7 (Sarstedt et al., 2021). Regarding the convergent validity, the AVE value was greater than 0.5, confirming that the constructs explain sufficient variance in their indicators (Sarstedt et al., 2021). Finally, we assessed the discriminant validity via HTMT, Fornell-Larcker Criterion, and cross-loadings. The result shows that the highest HTMT value of 0.83 for P_{eu} & P_{comp} and lower for others (see Appendix Table 1a) indicates the distinctiveness of constructs (Henseler et al., 2015). Our model establishes discriminant validity since all HTMT values are significantly below the conservative cut-off value of 0.85 (Ringle et al., 2023).

On the other hand, the result of the Fornell-Larcker Criterion (see Appendix Table 1b) confirmed that constructs share more variance with their indicators than with others, as demonstrated by the diagonal values, which is the square root of AVE are higher than off-diagonal correlations (Ringle et al., 2023). The cross-loading used to assess discriminant validity demonstrated that each indicator loads higher on its intended construct than on any other construct (Supplementary Material Table 2). Overall, the PLS-SEM measurement model meets the indicator reliability, internal consistency reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity requirements.

4.2.2. Structural model

Following Hair et al. (2022), the structural model assessment was conducted by evaluating collinearity among predictor variables, predictive power and model fit. We first tested the predictive power of core TPB factors (see Supplementary Material Table 5). While these factors remained significant across all groups in the original TPB model, the

inclusion of TPB extension factors altered the influence of core TPB factors on behavioural intention, with some factors becoming insignificant. In this section, we focused on the full model, which incorporates both core TPB factors and their extensions while controlling for the countries' dummy and socioeconomic variables. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) results (see Supplementary Material Table 3) indicate that the maximum value is 2.831, confirming that there are no major collinearity concerns among the predictors, as this value is well below the threshold of 5 (Hair et al., 2021). The predictive power of the model, measured by the coefficient of determination (R^2), is 0.614 for the complete sample and ranges from 0.473 to 0.721 for the subgroup models (Table 2). These results indicate moderate to good predictive ability of the structural model for CSA-practice adopters and CSA-technology adopters. In contrast, the predictive ability is still satisfactory for the non-adopter group (Mehmetoglu and Venturini, 2021).

Regarding the model fit assessment (see Supplementary Material Table 4), the full model showed a slightly better fit than the model that only considered the behavioural factors, as evaluated using Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), Chi-Square, Normed Fit Index (NFI), and other fit indices (Stone, 2021). Furthermore, higher Q^2 Predict values confirm that the full model generalizes better for out-of-sample predictions in different contexts of CSA adoption behaviour. Thus, based on the model fit assessment and the integration of additional socioeconomic variables and country-level variations—as other countries exhibit varying CSA adoption behaviours due to policy differences—this paper presents and interprets results based on the full model. The results from the model that focused only on behavioural factors without controlling socioeconomic variables were presented in the Supplementary Material Table 6.

Table 2 presents the structural model results based on the full model, examining the relationships between behavioural factors and future CSA adoption intentions. The analysis was conducted for three groups—non-adopters, CSA practice adopters, and CSA technology adopters—and for the complete pooled sample. The findings confirm that the core TPB factor—attitudes (H1)—demonstrates a significant relationship across all groups, while perceived behavioral control (PBC) (H3) shows a significant relationship among non-adopters, CSA practice adopters, and in

Table 1
Measurement model assessment.

Constructs	Indicators	Factor loading	Reliability and validity statistics
Adoption intention (Intent)	I plan to adopt a climate-smart agriculture (CSA) practice or technology (inten1).	0.903	$\alpha = 0.904$ CR(rho_a) = 0.905 CR(rho_c) = 0.940 AVE = 0.839
	I intend to use a CSA practice or technology over the next five years (inten2).	0.932	
	I will regularly try to apply CSA practice or technology in the near future (inten3)	0.913	
Perceived behavioural control (PBC)	I have the ability to implement a CSA practice/technology (pbc1)	0.864	$\alpha = 0.796$ CR(rho_a) = 0.802 CR(rho_c) = 0.880 AVE = 0.711
	If it were entirely up to me, I am confident that I will adopt a CSA practice/technology (pbc2)	0.846	
	I have the resources, time and willingness to apply a CSA on my farming activities (pbc3)	0.819	
Attitude towards CSA (Attit): If I am going to adopt climate-smart agriculture (CSA),	I believe that adopting CSA will lower production costs (attit1)	0.882	$\alpha = 0.922$ CR(rho_a) = 0.936 CR(rho_c) = 0.945 AVE = 0.81
	I believe that adopting CSA will increase productivity (attit2)	0.911	
	I believe that adopting CSA will reduce workload (attit3)	0.906	
	I believe that adopting CSA will be useful for farm operations (attit4)	0.901	
Social norms (Snorm)	Farmers similar to me mostly use CSA practice or technology (snorm1)	0.783	$\alpha = 0.849$ CR(rho_a) = 0.87 CR(rho_c) = 0.896 AVE = 0.684
	Farmers in my surroundings apply CSA practice or technology (snorm2)	0.834	
	People, who are important to me, would approve the use of a CSA practice or technology (snorm3)	0.854	
	People, whose opinion I value, think that I should apply a CSA practice or technology (snorm4)	0.836	
Perceived compatibility (Pcomp): If I am going to adopt climate-smart agriculture	I think that it will suit in the way I like to work (pcomp1)	0.944	$\alpha = 0.865$ CR(rho_a) = 0.87 CR(rho_c) = 0.937 AVE = 0.881
	I think that it will be consistent with the goals I find relevant (pcomp2)	0.933	
Perceived ease of use (Peu): If I am going to adopt climate-smart agriculture	I think that it will be easy to learn (peu1)	0.94	$\alpha = 0.938$ CR(rho_a) = 0.945 CR(rho_c) = 0.939 AVE = 0.889
	I think that it will be easy to control (peu2)	0.946	
	I think that it will be easy to understand how it is used (peu3)	0.943	
Farm business noneconomic motives (NonEconM): It is important to me that running	My farm business maintains the tradition of my family (fmnecon1) (dropped)	-	$\alpha = 0.833$ CR(rho_a) = 0.945 CR(rho_c) = 0.881 AVE = 0.65
	My farm business produces in an environmentally friendly way (fmnecon2)	0.905	
	My farm business produces with care for animal welfare (fmnecon3)	0.857	
	My farm business produces fairly priced products (fmnecon4)	0.840	

Table 1 (continued)

Constructs	Indicators	Factor loading	Reliability and validity statistics
Farm business economic motives (EconM): It is important to me that running	My farm business produces with care for public health (fmnecon5)	0.891	
	My farm business has low production costs (fmecon1) (dropped)	-	$\alpha = 0.897$ CR(rho_a) = 0.908 CR(rho_c) = 0.928 AVE = 0.767
	My farm business results in high yields (fmecon2)	0.806	
	My farm business results in a high income (fmecon3)	0.792	
	My farm business produces the highest quality products (fmecon4) (dropped)	-	
	My farm business has low labour need (fmecon5)	0.858	
Risk aversion (RiskAv): When I take decisions concerning my farming business	My farm business is good for the employment in my rural area (fmecon6)	0.765	
	I prefer certainty over uncertainty	0.955	$\alpha = 0.749$ CR(rho_a) = 0.938 CR(rho_c) = 0.867 AVE = 0.767
Agri-training and advisory networks use (Train)	I avoid risks in my investments	0.760	$\alpha = 0.891$ CR(rho_a) = 0.901 CR(rho_c) = 0.920 AVE = 0.698
	I like to take financial risks-reversed (dropped)	-	
	Extent of using farmer training as source for your agricultural training	0.733	
	Extent of using farm visits as source for your agricultural training	0.877	
	Extent of using field demonstrations as source for your agricultural training	0.869	
	Extent of using field/farmers days as source for your agricultural training	0.836	
	Extent of using workshops/open discussions as source for your agricultural training	0.767	
	Extent of using advisory services source for your agricultural training	0.747	

Note: α = Cronbach's alpha, CR (rho_a) = Composite reliability (rho_a), CR (rho_c) = Composite reliability (rho_c), AVE = Average variance extracted. Dropped items were excluded based on low factor loadings (<0.7).

the pooled sample. Both H1 and H3 are supported in the non-adopter, technology adopter, and pooled models, underscoring the importance of individual belief structures—such as perceived benefits and self-efficacy—in influencing CSA adoption decisions. Social norms (H2) significantly influence adoption intentions among non-adopters and, to a lesser extent, among technology adopters. The complete sample analysis also confirms a significant positive relationship between social norms and adoption intentions, supporting H2. Among the three core TPB factors, PBC and attitudes toward CSA emerge as the strongest and most consistent predictors across all groups, indicating that farmers' confidence in their abilities, perception of CSA benefits, and access to necessary resources strongly drive adoption decisions. However, the strong and significant relationship between social norms and the intention to start adopting CSA suggests that leveraging social influences can be particularly effective for non-adopters. This highlights the importance of balancing internal beliefs (attitudes and self-efficacy) and external influences (social norms) in shaping future CSA adoption decisions.

Among the TPB extensions, the proximal cognitive factor—perceived compatibility of CSA—significantly influences future CSA adoption decisions among CSA practice adopters and the pooled sample, supporting our hypothesis (H4). Meanwhile, the other proximal cognitive

Table 2

The relationship of behavioral factors with future CSA adoption decision-making based on the full model.

Relationship	Practice Adopters		Technology Adopters		Non-adopters		Complete	
	Coeff (P-value)	Hypothesis	Coeff (P-value)	Hypothesis	Coeff (P-value)	Hypothesis	Coeff (P-value)	Hypothesis
Attit → Intent	0.189 (0.005)	H1-supported	0.258 (0.001)	H1-supported	0.241 (0.000)	H1-supported	0.194 (0.000)	H1-supported
Snorm → Intent	0.028 (0.309)	H2-not supported	0.100 (0.060)	H2-supported	0.208 (0.000)	H2-supported	0.143 (0.000)	H2-supported
PBC → Intent	0.297 (0.000)	H3-supported	0.074 (0.135)	H3-not supported	0.243 (0.000)	H3-supported	0.231 (0.000)	H3-supported
Pcomp → Intent	0.286 (0.000)	H4-supported	0.091 (0.138)	H4-not-supported	0.034 (0.325)	H4-not supported	0.142 (0.001)	H4-supported
Peu → Intent	0.205 (0.005)	H5-supported	0.233 (0.006)	H5-supported	0.150 (0.017)	H5-supported	0.133 (0.001)	H5-supported
EcoM → Intent	-0.089 (0.114)	H6-not supported	0.223 (0.004)	H6-supported	-0.011 (0.442)	H6-not supported	0.017 (0.341)	H6-not supported
NonEcoM → Intent	0.142 (0.049)	H7-supported	0.013 (0.438)	H7-not supported	0.068 (0.186)	H7-not supported	0.078 (0.037)	H7-supported
RAv → Intent	-0.048 (0.263)	H8-not supported	-0.154 (0.029)	H8-supported	-0.054 (0.166)	H8-not supported	-0.068 (0.019)	H8-supported
Train → Intent	0.042 (0.198)	H9-not supported	0.004 (0.474)	H9-not supported	0.002 (0.484)	H9-not supported	0.015 (0.308)	H9-not supported
CSA adoption category	No		No		No		Yes	
Socioeconomic variables	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Countries dummy	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Observations	170		152		369		691	
R-Square	0.721		0.716		0.473		0.614	

Notes: The values in brackets are p-values where * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Full model result that captures both behavioral and control socioeconomic and country dummy is presented in [Appendix Table 2](#).

factor—perceived ease of use of CSA—demonstrates a consistent and significant relationship with CSA adoption intentions, supporting H5. Notably, this relationship is relatively stronger among technology adopters, highlighting that perceived ease of use is particularly relevant for adopting CSA technologies. Among the TPB extension dispositional factors, farm business economic motives are significantly and positively associated with future CSA technology adoption decisions in the technology adopters' group, supporting H6. Meanwhile, non-economic motives significantly and positively influence the intention to continue implementing CSA among CSA practice adopters and the intention to start implementing CSA among non-adopters, supporting H7.

The last dispositional TPB extension factor considered in this study, risk aversion, shows a negative and significant influence on CSA adoption intentions in the technology adopters' group and the pooled sample, supporting H8. However, it is non-significant among non-adopters and CSA practice adopters, possibly due to differences in investment requirements and lower perceived financial risks associated with CSA practices compared to CSA technologies. Of the external conditions considered in this study, the extent of utilizing agricultural training and advisory services was hypothesized to influence future CSA adoption decisions significantly. However, the results indicate that training and advisory services did not significantly impact all groups, meaning H9 is not supported. This may be due to limited accessibility, a mismatch between training content and farmers' needs, or the perception that advisory services do not provide sufficient practical value for CSA implementation. Additionally, in the complete sample analysis, we controlled CSA adoption experience using a dummy variable, and the results show that CSA implementation experience positively influences future adoption decisions. This finding underscores the role of hands-on experience in fostering future adoption, reinforcing the idea that prior exposure to CSA practices enhances farmers' willingness to continue implementation. Furthermore, this result supports our research premise that future adoption decisions may vary based on farmers' CSA implementation experience, highlighting the importance of MGA analysis based on CSA implementation status.

Control variables (age, education level and farm holding size) showed a mixed influence on future adoption intention for CSA across groups (see [Appendix Table 2](#)). For instance, compared to respondents

less than 30 years old, adoption intentions for non-adopters and pooled samples were lower for respondents in the older age groups (50–59 and 60+ years). Regarding farm size and CSA Adoption, respondents having larger farms (>50 ha) significant and higher CSA adoption in technology adopters and the pooled sample as compared to respondents having farm size <50 ha, reinforcing the idea that larger-scale farmers are more likely to invest in CSA innovations. Regarding education, compared to respondents with secondary school education levels and those below, the respondents with higher education levels (bachelor's degree and above) have higher adoption intentions in the pooled sample. Still, they are not significant in individual adoption groups. Cooperative membership was included to capture its potential role in facilitating knowledge sharing and thereby enhancing the intention to adopt CSA. However, it did not show a significant effect across any of the groups in this study. The last control variable, the country dummy, was included in the structural model to capture unobserved heterogeneity. As highlighted by the results, compared to Denmark, respondents from Spain and Slovenia exhibit significantly higher adoption intentions in the non-adopters group. In contrast, respondents from Lithuania show significantly lower adoption intentions in both the CSA practice and technology adopters' groups, which may be attributed to constraints, like technical knowledge, or advisory services. However, respondents from the Netherlands display mixed and mostly non-significant results compared to Denmark, suggesting that CSA adoption intention patterns in these two countries are relatively similar. Controlling for these country-level differences highlights the importance of context-specific socioeconomic and regional factors in shaping future CSA adoption decisions.

4.2.3. Multi-group analysis (MGA)

In addition to the structural model results presented in [Table 2](#), [Table 3](#) provides the findings of MGA, highlighting significant differences in the influence of behavioural factors on future CSA adoption decisions across three groups: CSA practice adopters, CSA technology adopters, and non-adopters. This MGA result offers deeper insights into how behavioral constructs influence differently across adoption groups. When comparing CSA practice adopters to non-adopters, social norms significantly influence non-adopters more than practice adopters

Table 3
Bootstrap Multi-group analysis (MGA) results for behavioral factors based on full model.

Relationship	Difference (Practice adopters vs. non-adopters)	Difference (Technology adopters vs. non- adopters)	Difference (Practice adopters vs. Technology adopters)
	Coeff (P-value)	Coeff (P-value)	Coeff (P-value)
Attit → Intent	−0.052 (0.301)	0.017 (0.435)	−0.069 (0.267)
Snorm → Intent	−0.180 (0.016)	−0.108 (0.108)	−0.072 (0.199)
PBC → Intent	0.054 (0.283)	−0.169 (0.039)	0.223 (0.010)
Pcomp → Intent	0.252 (0.020)	0.057 (0.330)	0.195 (0.047)
Peu → Intent	0.055 (0.315)	0.083 (0.248)	−0.028 (0.410)
EcoM → Intent	−0.078 (0.250)	0.233 (0.031)	−0.311 (0.003)
NonEcoM → Intent	0.074 (0.279)	−0.054 (0.338)	0.129 (0.143)
RAv → Intent	0.006 (0.141)	−0.100 (0.159)	0.106 (0.034)
Train → Intent	0.040 (0.277)	0.002 (0.473)	0.038 (0.301)

Notes: The values in the brackets are *p*-values where **p* < 0.05, ***p* < 0.01, ****p* < 0.001.

The full model results of MGA, including socioeconomic variables and country dummy, are presented in [Appendix Table 3](#).

(−0.180, *p* = 0.016), emphasizing the role of social and peer influences in shaping future adoption decisions. This suggests that non-adopters rely more on social learning from other farmers when considering CSA adoption. Additionally, perceived compatibility is significantly more influential for practice adopters (0.252, *p* = 0.020), indicating that alignment with existing farming systems is crucial for those already engaged in CSA. In the case of CSA technology adopters versus non-adopters, economic motives are significantly stronger for technology adopters (0.233, *p* = 0.031), reinforcing the idea that financial considerations play a primary role in CSA technology adoption. Conversely, PBC has significantly lower influence on adoption intention for technology adopters than non-adopters (−0.169, *p* = 0.039). This suggests that non-adopters feel a greater need for control, resources, or external support before committing to CSA technologies, whereas technology adopters, having already engaged with these innovations, are less constrained by perceived control issues.

When comparing the behavioral factors influence between CSA practice adopters to CSA technology adopters, PBC has a significantly stronger influence on practice adopters (0.223, *p* = 0.010), implying that self-confidence in implementing CSA is more important for those adopting CSA practices. Since CSA practices tend to be labour-intensive and require personal effort, farmers must feel capable, confident, and able to allocate time and resources for implementation. In contrast, CSA technologies often reduce labour dependency, shifting the focus from personal control over labour to external factors, such as financial and technical support. This could lower the influence of PBC on technology adoption intentions. Similarly, perceived compatibility has a stronger impact on practice adopters (0.195, *p* = 0.047), indicating that the seamless integration of CSA into existing farming operations is a stronger driver for those adopting CSA practices. In contrast, economic motives are more critical for technology adopters (−0.311, *p* = 0.003), further supporting the idea that financial incentives and cost-benefit considerations play a key role when farmers choose to adopt CSA technologies. Finally, risk aversion is significantly higher for technology adopters compared to practice adopters (0.106, *p* = 0.034). This indicates that farmers adopting CSA technologies tend to be more risk-averse. One possible explanation is that CSA technologies often require substantial financial investment, making risk-averse farmers more cautious in their adoption decisions. The uncertainty regarding long-term returns on investment (ROI) and potential technical failures

could further heighten risk concerns among technology adopters.

The controlled variables also exhibit mixed effects in the MGA across CSA adoption groups (see [Appendix Table 3](#)). Age significantly influences future adoption decisions in some groups. For instance, compared to respondents younger than 30 years, those aged 40–49 years demonstrate significantly higher CSA practice adoption intentions than non-adopters. The country dummy variables in the MGA results also reveal notable regional differences between adopters and non-adopters. For instance, compared to Denmark, respondents from Lithuania and Slovenia exhibit significantly lower adoption intentions in the CSA practice adopter group than in the non-adopter group.

5. Discussions

By following the extended TPB framework, this study highlights the behavioural factors influencing farmers' decisions to adopt CSA across different adoption groups. Thus, the role of behavioural factors employed is discussed in this section. In addition, the implications and limitations of this study are discussed.

5.1. The role of core TPB factors

Interestingly, while the core TPB factors remained significant across all groups in the original TPB model (see [Supplementary Material Table 5](#)), their effects became weaker or non-significant in the extended model with additional TPB extensions and control socioeconomic factors. This shift suggests that TPB's socio-psychological factors do not solely drive farmers' decision-making but are also shaped by broader contextual influences. These findings highlight the need to balance internal psychological constructs—whether they relate to a specific technology or reflect more general beliefs and external opportunities, such as advisory and training services—that influence farmers' adoption behaviour ([Nguyen and Drakou, 2021](#)). This broader perspective offers a more comprehensive understanding of CSA adoption.

The MGA results in [Table 3](#) reveal that the decision-making process varies significantly between non-adopters, CSA practice adopters, and CSA technology adopters. Unlike previous studies that focused on pooled farmer groups, our approach uncovers group-specific motivations and barriers. The attitude towards CSA is a significant driver of adoption intention across the different groups. This suggests that internal positive belief in the benefits of adopting CSA, such as increased productivity, cost reduction and labour saving, are important for initiating the intention to start adopting and continuing implementation of CSA. This aligns with studies demonstrating that farmers' positive attitude toward CSA increases intention to adopt, indicating farmers are more likely to engage in the corresponding behaviour when they believe that engaging in this behaviour brings expected positive outcomes ([Li et al., 2020](#)). Also, the significant influence of the two core TPB constructs on adoption intention is supported by earlier findings regarding the intention to adopt nutrient best management practices ([Doran et al., 2020](#)) and smart farming technologies ([Feisthauer et al., 2024](#)).

PBC, reflecting farmers' confidence in their ability and resources to implement CSA, remains an important predictor for all groups except CSA technology adopters. This suggests that farmers who perceive greater control over CSA implementation—whether in terms of skills, financial capacity, or time availability—are more likely to adopt or continue using CSA practices and technologies. This finding aligns with previous findings by [Doran et al. \(2020\)](#), which revealed that PBC has the most significant influence on adopting sustainable farming practices. However, PBC has an insignificant influence on the intention to adopt CSA technology. This implies that while internal confidence in the availability of resources and capabilities may be weak, interventions focusing on external support mechanisms—such as hands-on training, subsidies, and institutional support—could better motivate participation in pro-environmental behaviors ([Barnes et al., 2019b](#)). This underscores the necessity of interventions that enhance farmers' confidence through

targeted incentives and technical support programs; implementation of CSA technologies demands more technical skill and is more expensive (Giua et al., 2022).

The perceived social norm, which captures social learning from the farmers in their surroundings and confirmation from people who are essential to the farmers, influences the non-adopters decision-making process to start implementing CSA and has a weaker association with the decision to continue implementing CSA for the current adopters. This suggests that peer influence in terms of learning and validation plays a crucial role in initial adoption decision-making, but it seems less impactful once farmers have hands-on experience. This is consistent with innovation theory, which states that early adopters rely heavily on social proof, while experienced users depend more on direct experience and perceived benefits (Rogers, 2003). This finding highlights the importance of external social validation for non-adopters, implying that targeted interventions and tailored messaging could help promote CSA adoption among farmers who have not yet implemented these practices, as suggested by Perry et al. (2021). These results are in line with Moons et al. (2022), who found that farmers' subjective norms strongly influenced farmers' adoption intentions in the context of bio-based fertilizer adoption.

5.2. The role of proximal TPB extension factors

Of the proximal factors, there is a significant positive association of the perceived compatibility of CSA with future CSA adoption decision-making for farmers who have already implemented CSA practices, but it is not significant for non-adopters and technology adopters. This implies that the greater the alignment of CSA practices with farmers' preferred ways of working and goals, the greater the likelihood of their continued adoption. This may suggest that farmers are more likely to continue using CSA practices if they perceive them to be compatible with their existing farming systems and practices. This highlights that compatibility is crucial for practice adopters, indicating that the seamless integration of CSA practices into existing farming systems is pivotal for their continued adoption. It aligns with previous research demonstrating the positive effect of compatibility with existing production methods on adoption intention (Moons et al., 2022). The other proximal cognitive factor is the positive and significant association of perceived ease of use with CSA adoption intention across the adoption groups. Even though the influence of perceived ease of use is not significantly different across groups, it has a relatively higher influence on the CSA technology adopter group. This may be due to how easily farmers can integrate these innovations into their workflows, which could be affected by their exposure and hands-on experience, which increases their likelihood of ongoing implementation. This aligns with the TAM, which shows that perceived ease of use influences continued usage more than initial adoption (Kirungi et al., 2023). This was supported by the findings that underscore the importance of implementing CSA with experiential learning opportunities as motivating factors for CSA adoption (Vallejos B et al., 2023).

5.3. The role of dispositional TPB extension factors

A dispositional factor, farm business motives, significantly influence farmers' CSA adoption decisions, albeit with mixed effects across different groups. To better understand these motivations, we distinguished pure economic motives from non-economic motives, ensuring a more nuanced analysis of their influence on adoption behaviour.

Non-economic motives, which are measured through indicators capturing environmental sustainability, ethical farming practices, and social responsibility, significantly influence the future adoption decisions of CSA practice adopters and pooled groups. This underscores the importance of promoting CSA beyond mere profitability, as farmers with strong environmental and societal values are more inclined toward sustained implementation of CSA practices. Thus, considering a farmer's

general farm business goals, a broader range of non-economic dimensions, such as farmers' motives for producing in environmentally friendly ways, ensuring fairness, and promoting public health care, could further drive farmers' adoption decision-making. Our findings align with Thompson et al. (2022), who demonstrated a positive association between non-economic environmental farm business objectives and the adoption intensity of sustainable agricultural practices in Europe. Recognizing the importance of intrinsic values in driving the adoption decision, this study highlights the interventions and policies that emphasize the societal and ecological benefits of CSA, thereby appealing to farmers motivated by broader ethical and environmental considerations.

The farm business economic motive, which is measured through financial incentives, productivity, and cost efficiency, plays a dominant role in CSA technology adoption, as demonstrated by MGA results. Farmers prioritizing economic goals are more likely to adopt CSA technologies driven by financial incentives, cost savings, and productivity enhancements. Our findings underscore that reinforcing economic motives among farmers who have already implemented CSA technologies can sustain their engagement and encourage further adoption. These findings align with Trujillo-Barrera et al. (2016), who demonstrated a positive relationship between economic motives and the decision to invest in sustainable agricultural technology. Furthermore, as indicated by earlier research (e.g., Ferraro and Price, 2013), farmers' economic motives play a key role in driving their decision to adopt sustainable agricultural technology. Our result suggests that to promote CSA adoption further, policies should focus on providing financial support mechanisms, such as subsidies, cost-sharing programs, or market incentives, to address the economic priorities of technology adopters. Additionally, integrating both economic and non-economic motivational strategies could foster more widespread CSA adoption across diverse farmer groups.

5.4. The role of control socioeconomic variables and country differences in CSA adoption

Even though the control variables employed in this study showed a mixed influence on future CSA adoption intentions across different groups, they provide crucial insights. Age differences play a significant role, as younger farmers exhibit a higher intention to adopt CSA compared to older farmers. This aligns with previous studies (Giua et al., 2022), which suggest that younger farmers are generally more open to innovation due to greater adaptability, willingness to take risks, and exposure to new agricultural technologies. Farm size also plays a critical role in CSA adoption decisions, particularly regarding CSA technologies, which is in line with Despotović et al. (2019). Our MGA results confirm that larger-scale farmers are more likely to invest in CSA technologies, reinforcing the idea that financial capacity, economies of scale, and resource availability influence CSA technology adoption (Barnes et al., 2019b).

Additionally, the inclusion of country dummy variables in the structural model analysis was essential for capturing unobserved heterogeneity across the five EU countries in our sample. While the primary focus of this study is not comparative country-level analysis, considering the country as a control variable in the structural equation model enhances the robustness of our findings by accounting for potential contextual and institutional variations that may affect CSA adoption patterns. The significant variation in CSA adoption across countries, as demonstrated by the coefficients of the included country dummies, underscores the importance of regional socioeconomic factors in shaping future adoption decisions. Controlling country-level differences thus ensures that the behavioral factors analyzed in this study remain the central determinants of CSA adoption while also recognizing the broader structural and policy-related influences that may vary across European agricultural contexts.

5.5. Implications of this study

The findings of this study highlight the importance of balancing internal psychological beliefs (attitudes, PBC, perceived complexity and ease to use, and farming motives) with external influences (perceived social norms and support conditions) in shaping farmers' future decisions to adopt CSA, focusing on MGA. The MGA findings further reinforce that CSA adoption intention is not influenced uniformly by these factors across all farmers, necessitating group-specific adoption strategies tailored to different behavioral drivers for current non-adopters of CSA. In this regard, adoption decisions towards CSA could be enabled by providing incentives, technical support, or training, as farmers seem to view these incentives positively (Barnes et al., 2019). Interventions or initiatives on motivations and awareness creation (De Lauwere et al., 2022), training, and technical support further help to overcome the perceived complexity of CSA (Feisthauer et al., 2024) and interventions to strengthen a positive attitude towards behavior (Barnes et al., 2019) could be helpful for non-adopters. To build positive norms amongst local farmers and positively increase awareness, extension interventions leveraging local networks, such as farmer knowledge transfer, were suggested (O'Donoghue et al., 2024). Thus, targeted dissemination to increase awareness through farmer field days, demonstration farms, and participatory learning platforms can potentially enhance CSA knowledge and confidence for non-adopters, as they may not fully understand the benefits of CSA. More importantly, social norms are identified as a driver of future adoption decision-making for CSA for non-adopters. Thus, leveraging social norms and strengthening social networks via peer-to-peer learning programs amongst farmers, community-based advisory services, and farmer networks could enable non-adopters by motivating their future adoption decisions towards CSA as they learn from their peers. This can also be enabled by the successful mobilization of experiential knowledge (Sutherland et al., 2022). Thus, strengthening peer-to-peer learning through on-farm demonstration can be considered an enabling factor for non-adopters. At the same time, it is also regarded as a pioneering farmers to become skilled sources of advice (Sutherland and Marchand, 2021).

For those farmers already implementing CSA, interventions aiming at raising awareness are not effective as compared to those who have no experience in implementing it (De Lauwere et al., 2022); rather, interventions that enable farmers to sustain the implementation of CSA can be helpful. For instance, economic incentives in terms of subsidies or cost-sharing for CSA technologies (Barnes et al., 2019), market price incentives through climate-smart certification (Van Asseldonk et al., 2023), social recognition for more CSA practices adopters (Pedersen et al., 2024), regulatory pushes (De Lauwere et al., 2022) appear to drive intention to continue implementing CSA. In addition, emphasizing the compatibility of CSA with existing farming systems, advisory services should focus on demonstrating how CSA practices integrate into their existing farming routines. As sustaining CSA technologies implementation often requires technical expertise and initial investment, making the availability of specialized training, advisory services, and partnerships with agricultural technology providers could be potential initiatives to drive intention to continue implementing CSA. In addition, strengthening knowledge-sharing networks like regional CSA learning hubs can help CSA practice adopters refine and expand their CSA techniques. As economic motives are a key driver for technology adopters, financial mechanisms such as low-interest loans, tax reductions, and investment grants should be made available. To effectively promote CSA adoption, interventions must be holistic, context-specific, and behaviorally informed. Tailoring adoption strategies to different farmer profiles, addressing both psychological and structural factors, and ensuring

accessible CSA incentives and advisory services will be critical in accelerating the transition to sustainable and climate-smart food systems.

5.6. Limitations of the study and future research directions

While this study provides valuable insights into the behavioural factors influencing future CSA adoption decisions, some limitations need to be considered while interpreting the results. This study employed convenience sampling to draw the sample respondents through various distribution channels across five European countries, namely Denmark, the Netherlands, Spain, Lithuania, and Slovenia, which represent diverse agricultural systems. Although this sampling approach has its limitations, it allowed us to collect insights from a diverse range of farmers across multiple European agricultural systems within the Beatles project's timeframe. Even though research based on convenience samples can be necessary when sociocultural and other factors are expected to influence outcomes (Andrade, 2021), employing convenience sampling may introduce potential biases and affect the generalizability of the findings (Despotović et al., 2019). In our study, this was reflected by the demographic distribution of sample respondents, which is skewed towards young age groups and higher education levels, which may affect the generalizability of our findings. For instance, approximately 30 % of respondents were under 39 years old, potentially due to survey link distribution through farmer student networks in Denmark via the BEATLES project partner, which may have increased responses from future farmers. Even if we have included the country dummy and socioeconomic variables as a remedy predictors in the PLS-SEM structural model to control regional and other heterogeneity due to the uneven distribution of respondents across the countries, these may still limit the generalizability of findings. Therefore, caution should be taken while interpreting the findings. Notably, the study focuses on the differences between adopters and non-adopters in future adoption decision-making rather than capturing the behavioral factors associated with CSA adoption intentions through a country-wise analysis.

This study provides insights into understanding the factors influencing future CSA adoption decision-making by emphasizing adopter and non-adopters group-based analysis and suggesting a need for group-targeted behavioural interventions tailored to specific factors among farmer groups. However, it relies on stated intention measures rather than actual adoption behaviour, assuming that higher intentions will lead to adoption. However, some research suggests that intended behaviour does not always translate into real-world actions due to various constraints such as financial limitations, risk perception, or policy environments Niles et al. (2016). On the other hand, some research shows that intention is the main predictor of actual adoption (Bonke and Musshoff (2020)). Thus, we also expect higher intentions to lead to adopting CSA practices and technologies. However, future research should consider this by conducting longitudinal studies or using observed adoption behaviour data to validate the predictive power of behavioural intentions. Thirdly, while this study integrates socioeconomic factors (age, farm size, education level, and cooperative membership) as control variables, it seems partially explored as some other socioeconomic and policy variables, such as access to subsidies, market incentives, and policy environments were not explicitly included in the model. Future studies should expand the analysis to include these external constraints, which may further shape CSA adoption decisions.

Although this study incorporates a dispositional factor (e.g., risk aversion), it does not explicitly analyze psychological barriers such as uncertainty aversion. This may be due to the adopted items explicitly focusing only on the financial aspect. Future research should consider

including other dimensions of risk beyond economic concerns. The predictor included in influencing or modifying other behavioral factors is the extent of agricultural training and advisory services utilization. However, its influence is insignificant and exhibits a very low association. This may be due to the use of various sources of training and advisory services (workshops, field demonstrations, farm visits, advisory services, and training programs) as items to measure it, where some of them may not be widely used in services and sources by the sample respondents. This could also be attributed to the measurement approach used for this construct. Therefore, we cannot conclude that the extent of using different agricultural training and advisory services has no direct impact on adoption intention or no moderation effect on other behavioural factors. Thus, future research should consider identifying and prioritizing the dominant sources of agricultural training and advisory services in each country when including this predictor.

PLS-SEM is suitable for exploratory research, however it has certain limitations, such as sensitivity to measurement errors (Guenther et al., 2023). To ensure the robustness of our findings, we conducted a robustness check by employing Covariance-Based SEM (CB-SEM), comparing its results with PLS-SEM using the pooled sample. Although PLS-SEM demonstrated a slightly higher predictive capability ($R^2 = 0.614$) compared to CB-SEM ($R^2 = 0.540$), the CB-SEM results (see Supplementary Material Table 7) confirm that our core findings remain stable across both estimation methods. This aligns with previous research, which has shown that both CB-SEM and PLS-SEM tend to produce comparable results (Dash and Paul, 2021).

6. Concluding remarks

This study contributes to the growing literature on CSA adoption by examining the driving factors influencing future adoption decisions across three different farmer groups: namely **non-adopters** and **adopters of CSA practices** and **adopters of CSA technologies**. Our results confirmed that the original TPB factors predict CSA adoption decisions. However, our results also showed that additional factors in terms of proximal cognitive factors (perceived compatibility and perceived ease of use) as well as distal dispositional factors (economic and non-economic motives and risk aversion) also play a significant role in shaping adoption intentions. Thus, the extended TPB model provides a more holistic understanding of CSA adoption, going beyond the three core socio-psychological factors of the original TPB framework.

The findings confirm that core TPB constructs—attitudes, PBC, and social norms—remain significant predictors of adoption intention across all groups. However, their influence was reduced and or became non-significant when additional contextual behavioral factors, as well as socio-economic variables, were considered. This highlights the need to integrate both internal behavioral drivers and external support conditions when designing CSA adoption strategies. Specifically, the MGA results emphasize that CSA adoption is not uniform across farmer groups and that group-specific behavioral drivers and barriers exist. **For non-adopters**, social norms and positive attitudes serve as key motivators for initiating CSA adoption. This suggests that peer learning, advisory support, and community-based interventions could be effective tools for encouraging initial CSA adoption. **For CSA practice adopters**, perceived compatibility plays a crucial role in sustaining adoption. This

underscores the importance of ensuring seamless integration into existing farm systems, providing technical support, and promoting interventions that activate non-economic motives such as environmental sustainability and public health benefits. **For CSA technology adopters**, economic motives are dominant. Therefore, policies that provide financial incentives such as subsidies, credit systems, and market-based incentives (e.g., certification schemes), alongside technical training, could enhance adoption intentions and long-term engagement with CSA technologies.

Additionally, country-level differences could highlight the need for region-specific policy interventions that consider incentive mechanisms, knowledge accessibility, and advisory service gaps. The variation in CSA adoption across different EU countries suggests that CSA strategies should not be one-size-fits-all but rather tailored to specific national and regional contexts. Overall, this study suggests focusing on tailored group-specific interventions to enhance the future adoption of CSA.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Kassa Tarekegn Erekaló: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mariëna Gemtou:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Marcel Kornelis:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Søren Marcus Pedersen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Tove Christensen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Sigrid Denver:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Funding

This work was supported by the European Union via the BEATLES Project with Grant No. 101060645.

Declaration of competing interest

All authors have no competing interests to declare.

Acknowledgment

The authors express their gratitude to the respondents who participated in this study and to the BEATLES Project UCs that facilitated data collection. We are also grateful to the participants of the 98th Agricultural Economics Society Annual Conference for their valuable feedback on an early version of this article. Furthermore, we extend our thanks to the handling editor and the three anonymous reviewers for their constructive feedback, which has significantly improved the paper. Finally, we acknowledge the EU BEATLES Project for supporting this study under EU Grant No. 101060645. This study utilized the statistical software SmartPLS4 (<https://www.smartpls.com>).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.145632>.

Appendixes

Discriminant validity

Table 1a
Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

Relationship	Intent	Attit	Snorm	PBC	PEU	Pcomp	EconM	NonEonM	RAV
Intent									
Attit	0.595								
Snorm	0.545	0.412							
PBC	0.696	0.458	0.469						
PEU	0.617	0.762	0.41	0.515					
PComp	0.661	0.736	0.441	0.588	0.83				
EconM	0.28	0.367	0.164	0.318	0.331	0.341			
NonEonM	0.412	0.415	0.258	0.449	0.392	0.437	0.777		
RAV	0.063	0.197	0.066	0.142	0.19	0.217	0.596	0.551	
Train	0.314	0.249	0.357	0.246	0.239	0.243	0.211	0.271	0.07

Table 1b
Fornell-Larcker criterion

Relationship	Intent	Attit	Snorm	PBC	PEU	Pcomp	EconM	NonEonM	RAV	Train
Intent	0.916									
Attit	0.552	0.9								
Snorm	0.493	0.38	0.827							
PBC	0.594	0.4	0.395	0.843						
PEU	0.569	0.709	0.375	0.447	0.943					
PComp	0.586	0.662	0.387	0.492	0.749	0.938				
EconM	0.273	0.337	0.172	0.285	0.312	0.308	0.806			
NonEonM	0.375	0.384	0.246	0.385	0.362	0.387	0.728	0.874		
RAV	0.062	0.18	0.041	0.12	0.172	0.185	0.516	0.457	0.876	
Train	0.285	0.228	0.312	0.211	0.219	0.215	0.199	0.246	0.067	0.835

Table 2
Full model (for behavioral, control socioeconomic and country) with 10000 bootstrapping

Relationship	Practice Adopters	Technology Adopters	Non-Adopters	Complete
	Coeff (P-value)	Coeff (P-value)	Coeff (P-value)	Coeff (P-value)
Attit → Intent	0.189 (0.005)	0.258 (0.001)	0.241 (0.000)	0.194 (0.000)
Snorm → Intent	0.028 (0.309)	0.100 (0.060)	0.208 (0.000)	0.143 (0.000)
PBC → Intent	0.297 (0.000)	0.074 (0.135)	0.243 (0.000)	0.231 (0.000)
Pcomp → Intent	0.286 (0.000)	0.091 (0.138)	0.034 (0.325)	0.142 (0.001)
Peu → Intent	0.205 (0.005)	0.233 (0.006)	0.150 (0.017)	0.133 (0.001)
EcoM → Intent	-0.089 (0.114)	0.223 (0.004)	-0.011 (0.442)	0.017 (0.341)
NonEcoM → Intent	0.142 (0.049)	0.013 (0.438)	0.068 (0.186)	0.078 (0.037)
RAV → Intent	-0.048 (0.263)	-0.154 (0.029)	-0.054 (0.166)	-0.068 (0.019)
Train → Intent	0.042 (0.198)	0.004 (0.474)	0.002 (0.484)	0.015 (0.308)
Age_2 → Intent	-0.098 (0.289)	-0.425 (0.037)	-0.150 (0.152)	-0.194 (0.014)
Age_3 → Intent	0.003 (0.493)	-0.013 (0.468)	-0.368 (0.016)	-0.167 (0.032)
Age_4 → Intent	-0.028 (0.430)	-0.176 (0.143)	-0.337 (0.009)	-0.191 (0.009)
Age_5 → Intent	-0.266 (0.064)	0.119 (0.288)	-0.271 (0.031)	-0.153 (0.043)
Education_2 → Intent	-0.047 (0.378)	0.050 (0.392)	0.026 (0.412)	0.082 (0.132)
Education_3 → Intent	0.000 (0.500)	0.214 (0.110)	0.106 (0.164)	0.152 (0.017)
Farmsize_2 → Intent	0.114 (0.201)	0.248 (0.081)	0.091 (0.202)	0.122 (0.036)
Farmsize_3 → Intent	0.002 (0.492)	0.202 (0.071)	0.122 (0.139)	0.082 (0.091)
Coopm → Intent	0.112 (0.132)	0.225 (0.086)	-0.065 (0.274)	0.054 (0.190)
NL → Intent	-0.136 (0.236)	-0.222 (0.162)	0.251 (0.085)	0.041 (0.345)
ES → Intent	-0.063 (0.360)	-0.093 (0.310)	0.353 (0.023)	0.158 (0.054)
LT → Intent	-0.611 (0.000)	-0.413 (0.012)	-0.043 (0.396)	-0.229 (0.004)
SL → Intent	-0.203 (0.147)	0.074 (0.412)	0.471 (0.010)	0.214 (0.037)
CSA-experiene → Intent	-	-	-	0.330 (0.000)
R-Square	0.721	0.716	0.473	0.614

Notes: Base categories: Age = 1 (Age <30 years), Farm Size = 1 (Farm size <50 ha), Education = 1 (Secondary school and below), DK = 1 (country base category) and Cooperative membership = 1 (Yes), 0 (No).

The values in bracket are p-values where *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001.

Table 3
Bootstrap multi-group analysis (MGA) results for full model

Relationship	Difference (Practice adopters vs. non-adopters)	Difference (Technology adopters vs. non-adopters)	Difference (Practice adopters vs. Technology adopters)
Attit → Intent	-0.052 (0.301)	0.017 (0.435)	-0.069 (0.267)
Snorm → Intent	-0.180 (0.016)	-0.108 (0.108)	-0.072 (0.199)
PBC → Intent	0.054 (0.283)	-0.169 (0.039)	0.223 (0.010)
Pcomp → Intent	0.252 (0.020)	0.057 (0.330)	0.195 (0.047)
Peu → Intent	0.055 (0.315)	0.083 (0.248)	-0.028 (0.410)
EcoM → Intent	-0.078 (0.250)	0.233 (0.031)	-0.311 (0.003)
NonEcoM → Intent	0.074 (0.279)	-0.054 (0.338)	0.129 (0.143)
RAv → Intent	0.006 (0.141)	-0.100 (0.159)	0.106 (0.034)
Train → Intent	0.040 (0.277)	0.002 (0.473)	0.038 (0.301)
Age_2 → Intent	0.053 (0.412)	-0.275 (0.148)	0.327 (0.129)
Age_3 → Intent	0.371 (0.090)	0.354 (0.107)	0.016 (0.472)
Age_4 → Intent	0.309 (0.101)	0.160 (0.259)	0.149 (0.257)
Age_5 → Intent	0.006 (0.491)	0.390 (0.072)	-0.385 (0.079)
Education_2 → Intent	-0.073 (0.360)	0.024 (0.456)	-0.097 (0.340)
Education_3 → Intent	-0.106 (0.289)	0.108 (0.298)	-0.214 (0.176)
Farmsize_2 → Intent	0.023 (0.452)	0.158 (0.223)	-0.135 (0.270)
Farmsize_3 → Intent	-0.120 (0.255)	0.079 (0.341)	-0.199 (0.127)
Coopm → Intent	0.176 (0.156)	0.290 (0.078)	-0.114 (0.273)
NL → Intent	-0.387 (0.095)	-0.473 (0.070)	0.086 (0.384)
ES → Intent	-0.415 (0.069)	-0.446 (0.068)	0.031 (0.452)
LT → Intent	-0.568 (0.014)	-0.370 (0.090)	-0.198 (0.204)
SL → Intent	-0.673 (0.019)	-0.397 (0.145)	-0.277 (0.231)

Notes: Base categories: Age = 1 (Age <30 years), Farm Size = 1 (Farm size <50 ha), Education = 1 (Secondary school and below), DK = 1 (country base category) and Cooperative membership = 1 (Yes), 0 (No).

The values in bracket are p-values where *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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